

Influence of Light on Nitrification in Soil.

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In previous publications from these laboratories (Gopala Rao and Dhar, *Soil Sci.*, 1931, 31, 379 ; Dhar and Gopala Rao, *Sir P. C. Ray Comm. Vol., J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 81 ; Dhar, Bhattacharya and Biswas, *Soil Sci.*, 1933, 35, 281), it has been shown that nitrification in soils of tropical countries is more photochemical in nature than bacterial.

The object of this paper is (i) to show from exactly comparable experiments that the amounts of ammonium salts oxidised are much greater in presence of sunlight than in the dark with both sterilized and unsterilized soil ; the conditions for the experiments on nitrification were more or less similar to those occurring under natural conditions in the field; (ii) to show that more ammonia and nitrite are formed from urea and egg yellow in some in sunlight than in the dark; (iii) to show that the phenomenon of ammonification in soil is mainly an oxidation reaction accelerated by light, in case of temperature and aeration and soil surface and; (iv) to show briefly that the existing theories, explaining the increased production of ammonia and nitrate on drying the soil, on heating it or baking it in sunlight or sterilizing it by volatile antiseptics, are insufficient and to suggest a new explanation of the observations.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A hole was dug 9" deep in the grass land in the laboratory compound for the collection of the soil, which was not manured for some years. The soil was crushed, passed through a sieve with 1 mm. bore and dried in air at 80°. For sterilizing the soil, it was heated in an air-oven for 180 hours at 140°. All the chemicals and glass apparatus used in the experiments were sterilized in an autoclave at 20 lbs. pressure for an hour. The distilled water was sterilized by boiling.

For the nitrification experiments, 500 g. of the soil were mixed, with 5 g. of ammonium salts and 189 g. of sterilized distilled water exposed to light in loosely covered glass vessels or

about a year beginning from 2nd August 1932. During this period, on three occasions (10th August, 22nd October 1932 and 11th May 1933), 180 g. of sterilized distilled water were added and the soil containing the salts were carefully mixed up by stirring with sterile glass rod. Blank experiments under identical conditions were carried on in the dark by covering the glass vessels with a thick layer of black Japan enamel. For the experiments in the dark, these vessels were also placed in the sun to attain approximately the same temperature as those receiving sunlight.

After the completion of the exposure, the hard and dry soil was carefully powdered and 50 g. were taken out for analysis. The unchanged ammonium salt was estimated by adding potassium hydroxide in excess to the soil and distilling the ammonia set free and absorbing it with a standard solution of sulphuric acid. After the distillation of the ammonia, 1 g. of chemically pure Devarda's alloy was added to the soil containing alkali and the nitric nitrogen found by the oxidation of the ammonium salt was reduced to ammonia, which was distilled off and absorbed in sulphuric acid. In our experiments in order to drive off the first lot of ammonia, the flask containing the soil and ammonium salt and alkali was heated on a water-bath for more than 1 hour and then air was aspirated for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The reduction of the nitric nitrogen by Devarda's alloy was carried on for 1 hour and again air was aspirated for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. We have tested in our experiments that heating with caustic alkali for a longer period does not appreciably increase the amount of ammonia liberated.

For the experiments on ammonification with egg-yellow, fresh eggs were carefully washed with dilute solutions of potassium permanganate and broken with a sterile glass rod and the yellow was separated from the egg-white and a suspension was prepared in a sterile flask with sterilized distilled water. The suspension was mixed with different amounts of sterilized or unsterilized soil (or zinc oxide or titanium oxide) and exposed to light in 100 c.c. graduated cylinders. Another set was kept in the dark for comparison. Similar experiments were carried on with urea, which had already been sterilized by heating the solid in an autoclave. The loss of water due to evaporation was made up by the addition of sterile distilled water. These experiments were continued from November 1932 to March 1933. After the necessary exposure, the total nitrogen was estimated according to the method developed by Jodlbauer and Dyer

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(*cf.* Thorpe and Whiteley "Organic chemical analysis", 1926, p. 32). The ammonia formed from ammonification was estimated by Folin's method. The total amount of nitrogen in the egg-yellow suspension was determined by the Kjeldahl method before the exposure was started.

The soil with which all the experiments were carried on was analysed for its ammonia and nitric nitrogen contents in exactly the same way as described in the nitrification experiments. The amounts of NH_3 and NO_3 in 100 g. of soil are 0.006 g. and 0.0078 g. respectively.

The experimental results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Nitrification of ammonium salts exposed to sunlight for 550 hours.

Condition.	Nature of soil.	Amount of salt unoxidised.	Amount of salt oxidised.	Percentage oxidised.
Sunlight	unsterilized	NH_4Cl 1.9 g.	2.6 g.	59
Dark	..	4.2	0.7	14
Sunlight	sterilized	2.3	2.3	50
Dark	..	4.4	0.5	10.2
Sunlight	unsterilized	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ 1.85 g.	2.8 g.	60.2
Dark	..	4.4	0.55	11.1
Sunlight	sterilized	2.15	2.75	65
Dark	..	4.6	0.3	6
Sunlight	unsterilized	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ 3.35 g.	1.15 g.	29
Dark	..	4.75	0.15	3
Sunlight	unsterilized	4.2	0.8	16
Dark	..	4.85	0.1	2

In obtaining these values, corrections due to the presence of very small amounts of ammonia and nitrate present in the original soil have been introduced.

20 G. of the original soil when shaken with 20 c.c. of water gave a p_H value 7.3. The p_H of the exposed soils varied from 6.6 to 7.1. It was observed that the p_H of the soils receiving sunlight was slightly less than those in the dark. This was due to the fact that in the vessels receiving the solar radiations, there was greater oxidation of the ammonium salts and the consequent replacement of the basic radical by an acidic substance.

From the foregoing results it will be seen that the total amounts of the ammonium salts did not materially differ after a year from the amounts introduced. In presence of light, the amounts varied from 4.5 to 5 g.; in the dark the variation was much less and it was from 4.9 to 5 g. which was the amount introduced. Hence in our experiments specially in the dark, there was practically no loss due to denitrification. As the estimations of ammonia and nitric nitrogen in the original soil, in the soil kept in the dark and in the soil exposed to sunlight were carried on exactly in the same manner, the results obtained are certainly comparative.

TABLE II.

Ammonification and nitrification of 2 per cent urea solutions exposed to sunlight for 225 hours.

	Wt. of soil in g.	Percentage of ammonia formed.	Percentage of nitrite formed.		Wt. of soil in g.	Percentage of ammonia formed.	Percentage of nitrite formed.
Unsterilized	1 (light)	15.7	10.8	Sterilized	20 (light)	14.54	10.8
	1 (dark)	8	6.5		20 (dark)	6.7	4.58
Sterilized	1 (light)	14	9.4	Unsterilized	50 (light)	19.53	12.7
	1 (dark)	6.52	5.76		50 (dark)	12.7	
Unsterilized	20 (light)	18.0	12.8	Sterilized	50 (light)	18.5	17.98
	20 (dark)	12.1	10.1		50 (dark)	8.9	7.97

TABLE III.

Ammonification and nitrification of 2 per cent suspensions of egg-yellow exposed to sunlight for 225 hours.

Wt. of soil or catalyst in g.	Percentage of ammonia formed.	Percentage of nitrite formed.	Wt. of soil or catalyst in g.	Percentage of ammonia formed.	Percentage of nitrite formed.		
unsterilized	1 (light)	17.8	4.02	unsterilized	50 (light)	32.23	7.64
	1 (dark)	7.88	2.46		50 (dark)	26.7	6.23
sterilized	1 (light)	16.5	3.25	sterilized	50 (light)	27.85	8.33
	1 (dark)	9.45			50 (dark)	21.67	4.8
unsterilized	20 (light)	24.3	6.95	unsterilized	1 TiO ₂ (light)	4.93	...
	20 (dark)	16.5	2.45		1 TiO ₂ (dark)	3.31	...
sterilized	20 (light)	7.6	1.66	sterilized	1 ZnO(light)	6.38	1.66
	20 (dark)				1 ZnO(dark)	4.93	0

DISCUSSION.

These experiments were carried on in tall glass cylinders and hence the amount of air available was small and the percentage of ammonification and nitrification has not been large but the experimental results show that in presence of light, the amounts of ammonia and nitrate formed are always greater than those in the dark with both the sterilized and unsterilized soil. Moreover, the amounts of ammonia formed are always greater than the amounts of nitrite obtained. It is also apparent from the foregoing experiments that the amounts of ammonia and nitrite formed increase with the amounts of the soil. This happens because both ammonification and nitrification are increased by an increase of the surface on which oxidation can take place.

The experimental results in Table I show that on exposing the ammonium salts to light mixed with soil, the greater part of the ammonium compound is oxidised to nitrite after 550 hours' exposure

to sunlight with ammonium phosphate and chloride. The sulphate is much less oxidised. The oxidation in the vessels coated with black japan enamel is much smaller than in those receiving light. If nitrification were mainly a bacterial process, the amount of nitrification in the vessels in the dark with unsterilized soil should not have been materially different from those exposed to light.

Moreover, the amount of nitrite formed in the vessels with the sterilized soil is not very different from the vessels containing the unsterilized soil, the maximum difference in the percentage nitrified in the sterilized and unsterilized soils does not exceed 8 per cent. The germicidal property of sunlight seems to be well known. According to Warrington (*Chem. News*, 1877, 36, 263), light hinders the activity of nitrifying organisms. Waksman ("Microbiology", 1927, p. 35) has stated that due to the antiseptic properties of solar radiations, the number of bacteria is less on the surface of soils exposed to sunlight. We are determining the number of nitrifying bacteria in our samples of soil and from our preliminary results obtained according to the silicic acid gel method of Winogradsky, we find that the number of nitrifying bacteria in a gram of the original soil is not far from 8000. When the soil is exposed to sunlight, the bacteria are likely to be killed due to the joint action of light and increased temperature and that is why the amount of nitrification in the vessels exposed to light and containing unsterilized soil is not markedly different from those containing the sterilized soil. Moreover, the nitrification in the vessels kept in the dark and containing unsterilized soil is not widely different from those with the sterile soil. It seems likely that due to the high temperature also prevailing in the dark vessels, the bacteria could not survive.

As the light and dark experiments are exactly comparable, any bacterial contamination due to the introduction of air containing dust particles would affect the nitrification in all sets equally because the experiments were conducted at the same place. The results of our experiments, however, show that nitrification is only prominent in vessels receiving sunlight and this is not likely to be a matter of chance only. A similar behaviour is observed in the ammonification experiments.

Last summer we measured the soil temperature at Allahabad and in the month of April, it went up to 50° at two inches deep. May and June, 1933, were frequently cloudy and the summer was a mild one. In the months of May, June and July, 1932, after exposing

ammonium salt solutions mixed with soil to sunlight for 700 hours, we get oxidation of 80% with ammonium chloride and 89% with ammonium phosphate, whilst in the dark, the figures were 4.8% for ammonium chloride and 1.4% for ammonium phosphate (cf. Dhar, Bhattacharyya and Biswas, *loc. cit.*). The summer of 1932 at Allahabad was more severe than that of 1933 and that is why there was greater oxidation of ammonium salts in light in 1932 than in 1933. Moreover, there is another factor; in the experiments carried on in the months of May, June and July, 1932, this ammonium salts and soil were always kept wet by the frequent addition of water, whilst for the experiment recorded in this paper, the soil was allowed to dry up completely in order to have the experimental conditions similar to those occurring under natural conditions in the field. The oxidation of ammonium salts is greater in the wet condition of the soil than when it is hard and dry. Leather, working at Pusa, stated that the maximum temperature at Pusa may rise to 70° at the soil surface and 60° at the depth of 1 or 2 inches.

In Egypt the recorded temperature is 65° at the surface and 56° at a depth of 2 inches. From recent measurements in our laboratory on the influence of temperature on bacterial nitrification, we find that 35° is the optimum temperature for bacterial nitrification, which becomes practically negligible at 50° due to the harmful influence of high temperature on bacteria. Hence in tropics, nitrification in soil cannot be much of bacterial origin in the months of April, May, June and July. In these very months, the amount of nitrate in soils is, however, the greatest (Compare Dhar and Gopala Rao, *loc. cit.*). Even in colder countries like England, Germany, etc., the soil temperature may go up to 35° or more in summer (*Vide*, Russel, "Soil Conditions and Plant Growth", 1932, p. 468), although the optimum temperature for bacterial nitrification is stated to be 25° in cold countries. In these countries, bacterial nitrification must be greatly hindered in the summer months due to the soil temperature becoming much greater than the optimum temperature for bacterial nitrification, though the nitrate content of the soil in these countries is also largest in the summer time.

Dhar and Atma Ram (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 287) have shown that in the photo-oxidation of organic substances, specially the amino-acids and hydroxy compounds, appreciable amounts of formaldehyde are formed. The formaldehyde produced

in the photo-oxidation of organic compounds present in the soil is likely to hinder in the bacterial processes taking place in the soil due to the harmful influence of formaldehyde on micro-organisms and hence the nitrification in the soil due to bacteria will be curtailed by the presence of the formaldehyde, which is a powerful antiseptic and is produced in soil by the oxidation of the organic compounds by air in presence of light.

In a private communication to one of the authors, Dr. A. S. Corbet working at the Agricultural Research Station, Bracknell, Berkshire, makes the following statement, "From my experience in Malaya, where I was particularly struck by the paucity of soil micro-organisms, I should think your results on photo-nitrification are of quite general application in tropical countries".

In the unmanured soil of the Institute de Brie-Comte-Robert, Winogradsky found only a few living organisms, three or four kinds of cocci, a few azotobacter, some mycelium of actinomyces and a few yeast but no bacilli or moulds. These are regarded by Winogradsky as the normal population of the soil.

The foregoing observations make it clear that the process of nitrification in soils, specially in tropical countries, is certainly due more to sunlight than to bacteria.

Ammonification—an Oxidation Process.

In a recent communication (Dhar and Atma Ram, *loc. cit.*), it has been shown that aqueous solutions of amino-acids, like glycine, very readily form formaldehyde and ammonia and carbon dioxide when exposed to air and light:

Many years ago Otto Neubauer (*Deut. Archiv. klinische Medizin*, 1909, 95, 211) stated that in the animal body the process of ammonification or *de-amination* might be one of *oxidation* and not hydrolysis. The first stage in the process of *oxidative de-amination* can be represented as follows:

The first step in the oxidative de-amination from glycine is expected to be glyoxalic acid and from alanine pyruvic acid $CH_3COCOOH$.

That this method of oxidation is actually taking place in the animal body was evident when Neubauer gave phenylglycocoll to a dog and found phenylglyoxalic acid and mandelic acid in the urine.

Experiments in progress in these laboratories show the amounts of ammonia obtained on exposing solutions of amino-acids like glutamic acid, aspartic acid etc., to light, increase on passing air through the solutions of amino-acids. These are cases of oxidative de-amination. The formation of ammonia from these amino-acids is greatly increased by the presence of solid surfaces like ZnO , TiO_2 , SiO_2 etc.

It appears that in the soil as well, formation of ammonia from the amino-acids obtained from protein decomposition is, mainly an oxidative de-amination. The amino-acids have been readily oxidised *in vitro* by Palit and Dhar (cf. Dhar, "New Conceptions in Biochemistry," 1932) simply by passing air in presence of inductors like ferrous hydroxide, cerous hydroxide, sodium sulphite etc., and on charcoal surface by Warburg. Moreover, aqueous solutions of amino-acids are very easily oxidised by air in presence of light; the oxidation of glycine solutions by air is a highly photosensitive reaction. We are of the opinion, therefore, that the formation of ammonia in the soil is a surface reaction and an oxidation process taking place on the soil surface with liberation of energy. The amino-acids adsorbed on the soil surface are being oxidised to ammonia by the adsorbed oxygen of the air and this chemical change like the process of nitrification in soil can take place even without the presence of bacteria or fungi and is considerably accelerated by light.

This theory easily explains many obscure phenomena taking place in the soil. According to this view point any agency, which

increases either the soil surface or soil temperature or aeration or the amount of light falling on the soil, will lead to increased ammonia formation as well as nitrification.

According to Lathrop (*J. Franklin Inst.*, 1917, 183, 169, 303, 465), histidine, hypoxanthine, cytosine, xanthine, nucleic acid, creatinine, cyanuric acid etc., are of common occurrence in the soil. Marchal (*Bull. Acad. Roy. Sci. Belg.*, 1895, 27, 71) stated that the formation of ammonia from protein is favoured by increase of temperature, complete aeration and a slightly alkaline medium. Moreover, Gainey (*Soil Sci.*, 1919, 7, 293) reported that insufficient aeration and moisture resulted in a decrease in ammonia formation from dried blood and cotton seed meal. According to Temple (Compare Waksman, "Microbiology", 1927, p. 688), the differences obtained in ammonia formation in different soils are due to a number of causes other than the microbial flora of the soil.

That ammonification in soil is mainly an oxidation reaction is apparent from the statement of Terroin and Wurmser (*Compt. rend.*, 1922, 174, 1435 ; 1922, 175, 228) that a large loss of energy is associated with the process of ammonia formation in soil.

In recent experiments carried on in these laboratories it has been observed that the optimum temperature for bacterial ammonification of urea solutions in presence of soil is 40° ; the velocity of this process at 50° is exceedingly small and stops completely at 55°. Hence in tropical soil, very little of bacterial ammonification of urea is possible in the hot weather, as the soil temperature exceeds 60° in many cases.

In publications from these laboratories (Dhar, "New Conceptions in Biochemistry," p. 100) it has been emphasised that the oxidation of energy-rich substances by air *in vitro* and *in vivo* is markedly accelerated by alkali ; the same behaviour has been observed in the ammonification in soil as stated by Marchal.

An Explanation of Increased Soil Fertility on Partial Sterilization of Soil and on drying it.

The favourable influence of the drying of soil upon the growth of higher plants is well known. Different soils behave differently in this respect, heavy soils showing greater differences than light soils.

Burning the humus *in situ* sets free plant nutrients and accentuates nitrification. It is stated that in Sweden this step is taken for the regeneration of the soil.

The beneficial effect of fire upon soils has been reported by Worley (*Nature*, 1933, 131, 787) and Topham (*ibid.*, 1933, 132, 102). Similarly partial sterilization of soils leads to their increased fertility. According to Russel and Hutchinson (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1909, 3, 111; 1913, 5, 152) partial sterilization of soil by heating it to 60° or treatment with volatile antiseptics, increases the rate of oxidation in the soil. Russel ("Soil Conditions and Plant growth", 1932, p. 441) makes the following interesting statement on this point—"The fact has long been known to cultivators of the soil. Heating the soil has been practised from time immemorial in India, the process is called "rab" and is mentioned in the Vedas; the burning of stubble was known by the Romans to increase the fertility of the soil, and various possible explanations were shrewdly put forward by Virgil. Exposure of the soil to the baking heat of the sun is an ancient practice still common in India and in Egypt, where it is known as *sheraqui* and has been studied by J. A. Prescott and shown to be due partly to microbiological and partly to physical causes. Lebedjantzev considers that this repeated drying and heating of the soil plays no small part in maintaining its fertility in hot countries. *The effects on the plant are in all cases described as resembling those of nitrogenous manure*".

"*This increased production of ammonia and nitrate is not a necessary consequence of the higher numbers of organisms; on the contrary, higher numbers, e.g., those induced by adding non-nitrogenous organic matter to the soil, might depress the ammonia and nitrate content by taking up these substances for their own nutrition. The increased production of ammonia and nitrate is a distinct phenomenon and several explanations have been put forward to account for it.*" Waksman ("Microbiology", 1927, p. 746) states "sterilization by heat results also in the destruction of the nitrifying bacteria; it brings about a decided increase in the amount of ammonia accumulated in the soil".

"A large number of antiseptics bring about true partial sterilization with the following results:

1. The destruction of the protozoa and nitrifying organisms,

2. An initial increase of ammonia followed by a considerable increase in the rate of ammonia formation and consequently of soil productivity.

3. The complete or almost complete destruction of the soil fungi, of soil nematodes and other soil infesting worms and insects etc".

"It is sufficient to mention, among the volatile antiseptics, toluol, carbon disulphide and chloroform. Concentrations of 1 to 4 per cent of the disinfectant are allowed to act upon the soil for 12 to 48 hours, the soil is then aerated so that the disinfectant may evaporate".

From the foregoing quotations, it will be evident that the increased production of ammonia and nitrate on drying the soil, on heating it or sterilizing it by volatile antiseptics is not due to higher number of organisms in the soil. Hence the protozoan and other existing theories based on microbic action are insufficient to explain this increased soil fertility. The view advanced in this paper can satisfactorily explain this interesting observation based on experience. On drying, on heating and sterilizing with volatile antiseptics, the soil surface and the aeration are increased and hence the oxidation of the amino-acids by atmospheric oxygen leading to the liberation of ammonia and its subsequent oxidation are increased. Moreover, sunlight or diffused day light is always present and is accelerating the formation of ammonia from amino-acids and its oxidation to nitrite. It appears that the increased fertility on heating the soil or exposing it to sunlight as is done by cultivators in many countries is mainly due to increased oxidation of the nitrogenous compounds, mainly the amino-acids, by air causing the formation of ammonia and increased nitrification brought about by making the soil more porous and the accentuation of the air supply and increased soil temperature and above all by the light absorption.

It seems that both ammonification and nitrification in soil are oxidation reactions markedly accelerated by heat and light and both the processes may be actively going on in presence of light even in the absence of bacteria.

According to Maximov ("Plant Physiology", 1930, p. 50); Russian black soils contain 0.5% organic nitrogen, 0.02% ammoniacal nitrogen and 0.003% of nitric nitrogen. The grey forest soils contain 0.25, 0.001 and 0.0008% and the sandy soil, of Leningrad 0.09, 0.002 and 0.0009%.

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Wyatt, Ward and Newton (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1926, 7, 1) have stated that in the case of some soils rich in organic matter, as in the fertile prairie soils, the transformation of ammonia into nitrate is a slower reaction than the production of ammonia, which, therefore, increases in the soil.

It appears that in soils, the processes of ammonification and nitrification go on simultaneously, the velocity of the oxidation of the amino-acids forming ammonia appears to be greater than the velocity of the oxidation of the ammonium salts and ammonia to nitrite and nitrate by air and hence in many soils, the amount of nitric nitrogen present is less than that of ammoniacal nitrogen. Our experimental results obtained on exposing urea solutions and egg-yellow suspensions to light show that the amounts of ammonia formed are always greater than the amounts of nitrite produced. The soil with which our experiments have been performed contained more nitrate than ammonia, perhaps due to the greater oxidation of ammonium salts in presence of sunlight.

Further work on photo-ammonification and nitrification and bacterial count are in progress in these laboratories.

SUMMARY.

1. When ammonium salts mixed with sterilized or unsterilized soils are exposed to sunlight in contact with air for 550 hours, the exposure being spread over a year, the amounts of the ammonium salts oxidised to nitrite are as follows:

Ammonium chloride (sterilized soil)	...	...	... 65%.
" " (unsterilized soil)	...	...	... 58
Ammonium phosphate (sterilized soil)	...	...	... 55
" " (unsterilized soil)	...	...	... 60.2
Ammonium sulphate (sterilized soil)	...	...	... 16
" " (unsterilized soil)	...	...	... 28

The oxidation in the dark is much less and lies between 14 to 2%.

2. The amounts of ammonia and nitrite formed on exposing solutions of urea or suspensions of egg-yellow mixed with sterilized or unsterilized soil to sunlight for 224 hours are always greater in light than in the dark. The amounts of ammonia are greater than those of nitrite produced.

3. The optimum temperature for bacterial nitrification in hot countries is 35°, whilst the soil temperature in summer months may

be 70°. Hence nitrification in the summer cannot be appreciably due to bacteria, although the nitrate content of soil is greatest in the summer.

4. The formaldehyde formed in the photo-oxidation of organic compounds present in the soil is likely to exert harmful effect on the bacterial process taking place in the soil.

5. The process of ammonification in soil, that is, the formation of ammonia from the amino-acids obtained from protein decomposition appears to be mainly an oxidative de-amination taking place on the soil surface by the oxygen of air aided by light. Any agency, which increases either the soil surface or soil temperature or aeration or the amount of light falling on the soil, will cause increased ammonia formation as well as nitrification.

6. The increased production of ammonia and nitrate on drying the soil, on heating it or taking it in sunlight or sterilizing it by volatile antiseptics can not be explained from the protozoan and other existing theories based on microbial action, because all these processes lead to a decrease in the number of organisms present in the soil. The soil surface and aeration, however, are increased by these processes and hence the oxidation of amino-acids by atmospheric oxygen leading to the liberation of ammonia and its subsequent oxidation to nitrite are increased, these oxidations being accelerated by light.

7. It appears, therefore, that both ammonification and nitrification in soil are oxidation reactions markedly accelerated by light and heat and both these processes may actively go on in presence of light even in the absence of micro organisms.

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